

Groundwater research landscape of Jakarta Basin

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Abstract. Based on our experience, defining research topic and design is the hardest part in the research cycle. Many techniques have been introduced to make this stage easier. The following paper is the second part of our bibliometric project in the search for a gap in the water resources research in Jakarta. This paper starts to analyse the visualisations that had been extracted from the previous paper based on our database. Using the keyword “groundwater Jakarta”, we managed to get 70 relevant papers. Several visualisations have been built using open source applications. Word cloud analysis shows that the trend to discuss groundwater in scientific sense had only been started in the early 2000’s. This is presumably due to the emerging regional autonomy in which forcing regions to understand their groundwater setting before creating a management strategy. More papers in the later time has been induced by more geo-hazards (land subsidence and floods) resulted in the vast groundwater pumping. More and more resources have been utilized to get more groundwater data. Water scientists by then understood that these hazards had been started long before the 2000’s. This had become the starting point of data era later on. The next era will be the era of water management. Hydrologists had been proposing integrated water management Jakarta and its nearby groundwater basins.

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26 Most of them have been strongly suggested to manage all water bodies, rainfall,
27 surface water, and groundwater as one system. In the 2010's we identify more
28 papers are discussing in water quality following the vast discussion in water quantity
29 in the previous era. People have been more aware the importance of quality in
30 providing water system for the citizen. Then five years later, we believe that water
31 researchers have also put their mind in the interactions between surface water and
32 groundwater, especially in the riverbank, where most of the slums are located. Based
33 on the results, we believe that more researches to understand interactions between
34 groundwater and surface water would fill the gap to come up with better water
35 management system in Jakarta.

36 **1. Introduction**

37 Topic modelling and network visualization is a very important for researchers to
38 choose the least discussed topic and the gap in between research topics. To solve
39 the problem, we need to have a systematic extraction of topics and visualize it for
40 easy analysis[1,2]. This paper analyses the results from topic modelling and its
41 visualizations using open source applications: VosViewer[3] and Zotero and
42 PaperMachine plug in[4,5]. We brought a case in hydrogeological science, which
43 presents research landscape in Jakarta area. The work discussed in this paper was
44 mainly derived from our previous paper[6], which show case our topic modelling
45 technique.

46 **2. Methods**

47 This paper is the second part of our bibliometric work in which the first paper had
48 been published in RioJournal[6]. We're then try to give more analysis based on the
49 word cloud plots presented in the paper. We extract a reference database in RIS
50 format[8] using VosViewer software[9,10]. The original dataset and plots are available
51 on our Figshare Repository[7].

52 **3. Word cloud**

53 The basis of this analysis is the following word cloud plot using VosViewer software
54 (Figure 1). The trend to discuss groundwater in scientific sense had only been started

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56 which forcing regions to understand their groundwater setting before creating a
57 management strategy. Before 2000's, groundwater is placed as non-economical
58 goods.

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61 subsidence and floods) resulted in the vast groundwater pumping. More and more
62 resources have been utilized to get more groundwater data. Water scientists by then
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66 The next era will be the era of water management. Hydrologists had been proposing
67 integrated water management Jakarta and its nearby groundwater basins. Most of
68 them have been strongly suggested to manage all water bodies, rainfall, surface
69 water, and groundwater as one system.

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71 In the 2010's we identify more papers are discussing in water quality following the
72 vast discussion in water quantity in the previous era. People have been more aware
73 the importance of quality in providing water system for the citizen. Then five years
74 later, we believe that water researchers have also put their mind in the interactions
75 between surface water and groundwater, especially in the riverbank, where most of
76 the slums are located.

77 **4. Word connection**

78 Using Zotero reference manager, we managed to build word connections in the
79 paper collections (Figure 2). We thought this tool is very useful to understand the
80 nature of papers when they were written, instead of only relying on the keywords. We
81 can see that the word urban is highly connected to floods, ecosystem, development,
82 river, and river-rehabilitation. This, in a way, is referring the impacts of urban
83 development to the change of ecosystem, the modification of river environment, and
84 the rising frequency of flood hazards.

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Another word connection, “land – subsidence”, would be another way to look into the impact of excessive groundwater pumping, as has been in the perception of many since the early 2000’s. We don’t argue that this perception is vague, but this is likely due to the lack of researches in this subject. However more maps have been generated to identify the distribution of land subsidence, and try to connect the findings with the distribution of groundwater pumping.

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The next observed word connection is “groundwater - interactions, management, age, excessive (pumping)”. This indicates the rising awareness of groundwater as part of public goods, which needs to be managed. Hence defining its interaction with physical and social environment is very important. More problems in “water – supply” and “water – quality” are also important since more people means more water demand in high quality. Another word pair “subsurface – environments” is also notable in the plot. This is very interesting to us that the rising environmental problems before 2000’s have never been connected with subsurface environment. Regional planning documents released before 2000’s have been only occupied mainly by surface environment.

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5. Concluding remarks

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We believe that the year 2000 is the major milestone of groundwater research in Jakarta area, with the rise of regional autonomy. Our visualizations of bibliometric data shows that groundwater before 2000’s has only been placed as non-economical goods, which then shifted as the major spot of economical goods after the 2000’s. Such shifting has resulted to many geo-hazards, as perceived by the community. More and more unique keywords and word connections can be extracted since then with more environmental complication and social interaction. We also believe that more research should be directed to groundwater and river/surface water interaction to understand the nature of water quality in such megacity like Jakarta.

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Another take home note that we want to deliver is the importance of open source resources in academic life. More open source applications have been built to support researchers with lack of funding and sponsor. These open source applications as well

- 143 [3] N. J. P. Eck and L. Waltman, "VOSviewer: A computer program for bibliometric
144 mapping," ERIM Report Series Research in Management, 2009. [Online].
145 Available at: <http://repub.eur.nl/pub/14841/ERS-2009-005-LIS.pdf> [Accessed: 25-
146 Dec-2016].
- 147 [4] "Zotero: An open source reference manager." [Online]. Available at:
148 <https://www.zotero.org/> [Accessed: 25-Dec-2016].
- 149 [5] J. Guldi and C. J. Roberson, *Papermachines: a text mining plugin for Zotero*.
150 2011. [Online]. Available at: <http://papermachines.org> [Accessed: 25-Dec-2016].
- 151 [6] D. Irawan, A. Priyambodho, C. Rachmi, D. Wibowo, and A. Fahmi, "Bibliometric
152 study to assist research topic selection: a case from research design on Jakarta's
153 groundwater (part 1)," *Res. Ideas Outcomes*, vol. 2, p. e9841, Jul. 2016. [Online].
154 Available at: <http://riojournal.com/articles.php?id=9841> [Accessed: 25-Dec-2016].
- 155 [7] D. E. Irawan, A. Priyambodho, D. M. Wibowo, and A. K. Fahmi, "Literature
156 visualisation: Bibliometric of groundwater research in Jakarta," 2016. [Online].
157 Available at: <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.3405685.v3> [Accessed: 25-Dec-
158 2016].
- 159 [8] "RIS (file format)," *Wikipedia, the free encyclopedia*. 06-Jul-2016.
- 160 [9] N. J. Van Eck and L. Waltman, "Text mining and visualization using VOSviewer,"
161 *ArXiv Repository. ArXiv: 11092058*, 2011 [Online]. Available at:
162 <https://arxiv.org/abs/1109.2058> [Accessed: 25-Dec-2016].
- 163 [10] Z. Zahedi and N. J. Van Eck, "Visualizing readership activity of Mendeley users
164 using VOSviewer," in *altmetrics14: Expanding impacts and metrics, Workshop at*
165 *Web Science Conference, 2014*. [Online]. Available at:
166 [https://figshare.com/articles/Visualizing_readership_activity_of_Mendeley_users_](https://figshare.com/articles/Visualizing_readership_activity_of_Mendeley_users_using_VOSviewer/1041819)
167 [using_VOSviewer/1041819](https://figshare.com/articles/Visualizing_readership_activity_of_Mendeley_users_using_VOSviewer/1041819) [Accessed: 25-Dec-2016].